

A COMPARATIVE REVIEW ON KATUPIA GHRITA VIKESHIKA AND JATYADI GHRITA VIKESHIKA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DUSHTA VRANA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DIABETIC FOOT ULCER

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ABSTRACT

In India, the prevalence of diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) is significant, with studies showing rates around 6.2% to 12% among the people with diabetes, and an estimated 15-25% of diabetics developing them over time, highlighting a major health burden, especially with high costs and amputation risks, influenced by longer diabetes duration, male gender, and older age. The annual incidence can range from 1.0-4.1%. Dushta Vrana (chronic non-healing ulcer) is a frequent complication in diabetes mellitus, with significant morbidity due to delayed healing, infection, and recurrence.^[1] Diabetic foot ulcers are a common and serious problem in people with diabetes and are largely preventable. They cause significant suffering and reduce quality of life. Foot ulcers can lead to infection, repeated hospital admissions, limb amputation, and even death. Globally the lifetime risk of developing a foot ulcer in a person with diabetes is about 19%–34%, and this risk is increasing due to longer life expectancy and more complex diabetes. Once an ulcer develops, outcomes are poor. About 65% of patients develop another ulcer within 3–5 years, nearly 20% undergo lower-limb amputation during their lifetime, and 50%–70% die within five years after ulcer formation.^[2] Among Shashti Upakramas mentioned in classics, Sarpi is having both Vrana Shodhana and Ropana properties. Sushruta mentions 14 types of Vrana Bandhana for healing purpose in different forms like Vikeshika, Kavalika, Plota, Pichu, but these bandaging techniques are not widely used in clinical practice^[3] Traditional Ayurvedic formulations like Katupila Ghrita and Jatyadi Ghrita^[4] are used for wound care, but comparative clinical outcomes require systematic evaluation. Here, we shall discuss about the role of Katupila Ghrita Vikeshika dressing in the Management of Dushta Vrana with Special Reference to Diabetic Foot Ulcer.

KEYWORDS: Dushta vrana, katupila gritha vikeshika, Jathyadi gritha vikeshika, diabetic foot ulcer.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic foot ulcer is a chronic, often infected wound that aligns with the Ayurvedic concept of Dushta Vrana due to diabetes characterized by delayed healing, discharge, foul odor, pain variability, and altered margins and surrounding skin. The burden of Diabetic foot ulcer necessitates safe, affordable, and effective topical interventions. Katupila Ghrita and Jatyadi Ghrita are classical formulations with Vrana Shodhana (cleansing) and Vrana Ropana (healing) properties applied via

Vikeshika (medicated gauze). A comparative clinical study provides evidence to guide clinician choice between these two dressings.

Disease review of madhumehajanya dusta vran/ diabetic foot ulcer^[5]

Samprapti (Pathogenesis)

- The pathogenesis starts with chronic Madhumeha, which vitiates Kapha, Pitta, and Meda, impairs tissue

metabolism (dhatwagni), and affects Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Twak.

- Poor blood supply and neuropathy cause repeated injuries and infection. Vitiated doshas lodge at the site, leading to local tissue degeneration (Dushti of Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Rasa, Lasika).^[3]

- Formation of Prameha pidaka (diabetic boils) which evolve into Dushta Vrana if not properly managed.

- The disease passes through six stages as per shatkriyakaal (sanchaya, prakopa, prasara, sthanasamsraya, vyakti, bheda), culminating in chronic ulceration.

Mithyā Ahāra–Vihāra (Improper diet & lifestyle)

↓
Agnimandya (↓ Digestive & Metabolic fire)

↓
Āma Utpatti (Metabolic toxins)

↓
Kapha–Meda Vṛiddhi → Āvarana of Vāta

↓
Vāta Prakopa (esp. Vyāna, Apāna Vāta)

↓
Dhatukṣaya (Depletion of tissues)

↓
↓ Ojas, ↓ Rasa–Rakta–Māmsa–Meda Poshana

↓
Srotorodha (Obstruction in microchannels)

↓
Rasa–Rakta–Māmsa–Meda–Lasikavaha Srotas Duṣṭi

↓
Twak–Māmsa–Rakta Dhātu Duṣṭi

↓
Pāda Pradeśe Vāta Prādhānya (Neuropathy & ischemia)

↓
Vrana Utpatti (Ulcer formation)

↓
Kapha–Pitta Anubandha → Srava, Dourgandhya, Daha, Shopha

↓
Madhumehajanya Duṣṭa Vraṇa
(Chronic, non-healing, foul-smelling foot ulcer)

Poorva Rupa (Prodromal Symptoms)^[5]

- Numbness, tingling, and burning sensation in the feet.
- Loss of sensation (neuropathy) in lower limbs, predisposing to unnoticed trauma.
- Dryness and thinning of the skin in the feet.
- Discoloration and minor painless injuries which don't heal.

Samprapti Ghataka

Dosha: Tridoshaja with predominance of Kapha
Dushya: Tvak, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, vasa, Along with Dushyas involved in Madhumeha Samprapti
Agni: Jatharagni, Dhatvagni, Bhutagni
Agnidusti: Mandagni, Vishamagni, Tikshnagni (depending on predominance of Kapha, Vata, and Pitta respectively)
Ama: Mandagnijanya Ama

Srotas: Rasavaha srotas, Raktavaha srotas, Mamsavaha srotas, Medovaha srotas, Along with srotas involved in Madhumeha Samprapti

Vyaktasthana: Tvak

Adhisthana: Tvak

Rogamarga: Bahya Rogamarga

Svabhava: Chirakari / Dirghakalanubandhi

Prabhava: Yapyā.

Drug Review

- Katupilla: *Securinega leucopyrus*, (Willd) is described by the medico ethno botanist as a wonderful drug for the treatment of wound healing.
- Katupila (*Securinega leucopyrus* (Wild.) Muell) is a desert climate plant widely known in Sri Lanka as a traditional folk remedy which is used topically as paste for addressing acute, chronic, non-healing wounds and for other various disorders.
- It is known as Thumari and Katupila (*Securinega leucopyrus* (Wild.) Muell) in Srilanka.
- Studies indicate that *S. leucopyrus* possesses anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial and anti-oxidant and wound healing properties.
- It is used in the management of diabetic wounds with studies showing its effectiveness in promoting healing and reducing inflammation.^[6]

Preparations of Katupila Ghrita Vikeshika

Sterile clean leno-weave fabric gauze will be taken. It will be fixed into a double layered circular wooden ring and one layer coating of Katupila Ghrita is done uniformly with the help of cotton swab by gloved hands. This is kept inside the UV cabinet for drying and sterilization. After drying it is cut into 10x10 cm and sealed in polythene packs and stored at cool temperature (8°C to 15°C).

Procedure

• Purva karma

Cleaning of the wound and surrounding with normal saline and sterile gauze.

• Pradhana karma

Patient will be placed in a suitable position depending on the site of the lesion. Katupila Ghrita Vikeshika or Jatyadi Ghrita Vikeshika is placed over the wound sterile gauze pad is placed over the Vikeshika and bandaged.

• Paschat karma: Pathya explained.

DISCUSSION

The study compares two classical Ayurvedic wound dressings applied via Vikeshika for diabetic foot ulcer categorized as Dushta Vrana. Outcome domains reflect Vrana Shodhana and Ropana trajectories, including reduction of slough, promotion of healthy granulation, and contraction of margins.

Probable mode of action of Katupila Ghrita Vikeshika

Katupila Ghrita Vikeshika promotes healing of Dushta Vrana by its combined Shodhana and Ropana actions. Katupila, with its Tikta–Kashaya Rasa and Ushna Virya, helps reduce slough, discharge, infection, and excess Kleda by pacifying Kapha and Vata. Ghrita acts as a Yogavahi, enhancing penetration of the drug, maintaining a moist wound environment, and nourishing local tissues. The formulation exhibits antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects, promotes healthy granulation, angiogenesis, and epithelialization, thereby accelerating wound healing, especially in chronic diabetic foot ulcers.^[7]

CONCLUSION

standardized comparative protocol supports evidence-based selection between Katupila Ghrita and Jatyadi Ghrita Vikeshika dressings in diabetic foot ulcers, using robust clinical parameters over 21 days with follow-up for sustained healing. Final conclusions should be drawn after statistical analysis of collected data.

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